

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL BASIS OF THE MECHANISMS OF FORMATION OF ETHNO-PEDAGOGICAL STAFF AT THE STUDENTS OF A PEDAGOGICAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION

Rayimov Begali Uralovich

Termiz State Pedagogical Institute, teacher

Modern pedagogy uses various techniques and techniques in the process of educating the young generation. This will definitely contribute to the improvement of educational efficiency. For many years, our ancestors developed the main views, ideas and directions of raising children. These principles form the basis of such a science as ethno-pedagogy.

Every historically formed society has developed ideas about the process of educating young people. Ethno-pedagogy is a branch of science that teaches self-worth to the younger generation. Therefore, this approach allows children to learn about their cultural values from the earliest periods of their time. It is actively used in various educational institutions.

A common approach that interests children, as well as non-standard educational methods. In this case, new knowledge is acquired very quickly.

Ethnopedagogy is a branch of pedagogy that uses the historical experience of a particular nation. He is studying the opinions of the past generations on the issues of educating the younger generation. At the same time, great attention is paid to family, life, nation and nation.

The educational center of our country is distinguished by the diversity of cultural and historical values. Many ethnic groups have their own characteristics. Therefore, education takes into account such characteristics. The customs of all groups are not the same. But at the heart of every culture lie the same basic concepts and goals. The task of teachers is to teach children not a specific direction of historical experience, but the essence of many historical, cultural traditions,

traditions, songs and stories. This allows us to educate a person who interacts with society based on the principles of common values, thoughts and understanding.

In the conditions of modern technological development, it allows everyone to connect with the historical values given to him.

The concepts of ethno-pedagogy and folk pedagogy are not synonymous. The forefather of the science of inquiry applies a simple but effective logic to their education, focusing on the historical achievements of our ancestors.

Different researchers define the object and subject of ethno-pedagogy in a slightly different way. Thus, according to E. Khakimov, the object of this field is the educational process. The subject of research is the specific and specific processes of ethno-pedagogical knowledge acquisition.

Pesdemkovskaya GV says that such modern trends as scientific pedagogy are based on modern knowledge and research results. People's approach takes the foundation of everyday, everyday knowledge. Therefore, he believes that the object of studying ethno-pedagogy should be considered as folk culture. There is no scientific data on this traditional education. According to Pesdemkovskaya GV, the issue of ethno-pedagogy has a very broad social meaning. It consists of a traditional public education system.

GN Volkov, object of ethno-pedagogy selects folk culture and pedagogy. The research topic includes moral experience in the family, through ethnic creativity, words, stories, riddles, songs, etc. in the community.

In the process of studying ethno-pedagogy, specific goals and tasks are defined. Knowing them, you can learn more about the essence of this science.

The goal of ethno-pedagogy is to teach the young generation their values, civic consciousness, the system whose main principles have been developed during the life of our nation.

It is a priority to apply the traditions of different peoples living in our country to the educational process. Creative inspiration can be used in various fields of

activity. Ethno-pedagogy develops children's abilities, encourages self-expression and talent.

Certain tasks are being implemented to achieve these goals. This includes, first of all, the study of people's approaches to education. The task of ethno-pedagogy is to master the methods and methods of searching for methods and approaches in the implementation of such work, taking into account the characteristics of society.

Also, it is a task to control the relevance of scientific ideas presented to the field of education to the difficulties in educating a developed person today.

Ethnopedagogy science as one how many structural elements includes . _ _ Theirs between certain point of view from the point of view of the child physiology , spirit and social development learning detective work activity there is

Also this _ education methodology branch famous didactics . This teachings , instructions and of explanations the meaning open gives _ Also , there is a pedagogical deontology in ethnopedagogy , which is necessary , certain behavior norms , rules to perform to force learns _ This direction you your family , your ancestors , your history and your culture respect for you to do teaches .

Other structural unit is _ family pedagogy. This in the field ethnopedagogy to parents the children in education advice gives _ Modern in society this industry big to volume have _ This children in the mind , parents and to parents is worship .

Ethno- pedagogy this direction the children future weakness , marriage , marriage comrades between family to relationships prepares _ Offer done of science task not only of children , but theirs of their parents too is the doctrine . This study process done increase ways , methods and methods shows . Parents to his child moral concept , society with mutually relationships to understand pedagogical skills for to the basics have to be need _

Ethnopedagogy another sciences with closely depend _ This the most efficient has been new knowledge and skills is a complex approach to obtaining .

Ethno- pedagogy another sciences with tie up very important _ First of all , with ethnography mutually contact note reach need _ This knowledge field in the world peoples , their historical territorial membership again placing about information gives _

in the west of science this the field of ethnology is called His qualification , as well as every one of a person behavior , customs to learn includes . __ This certain in the area living known one of the group to himself special behavior account get enable gives _

Ethnopedagogy and ethnopsychology as well closely depends . People of knowledge this field one group of people their behavior _ character and mentality learns _ Ethnopsychology is specific of society representatives with each other with and those around you with mutually to relations effect doer factors learns _ This science certain of ethnicity emotional their field _ experiences and feelings represents _ From this besides , ethnopsychology in learning of people motivation as well as theirs social and psychological effects their to the activity effect shows .

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